

Ce doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles: An efficient visible light triggered photocatalyst with enhanced structural, optical and photocatalytic properties

Akilandeswari. S¹, Niranjana. M², Rajesh. G³

¹PG & Research Department of Physics, Government College for Women (Autonomous), Kumbakonam-612 001
Tamil Nadu, India.

²Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram-608 002, Tamil Nadu, India.

³Department of Chemical Engineering, Sri Sivasubramaniya Nadar College of Engineering, Chennai-603 001
Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract— In this present work, PbMoO₄ and Cerium (Ce) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles were prepared via a facile co-precipitation process. Multivalent Ce-PbMoO₄ nanoparticles were investigated for structural, optical and photocatalytic activities. XRD results confirmed the tetragonal structure of pure and Ce-PbMoO₄ nanoparticles. The crystallinity was further validated by SAED and XRD patterns. SEM analysis depicted spherical like morphology for the Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles. DRS spectra revealed substantial tuning of band gap from 3.12 to 2.33 eV with Ce doping owing to crystal defects. The photocatalytic capabilities of Ce doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles were assessed for the degradation of Brilliant Blue (BB) and Brilliant Green (BG) dyes under visible light irradiation of 120 min. This study also highlights the significance of oxygen vacancy-based surface defects in enhancing charge carrier trapping. The photodegradation was additionally confirmed by scavenger study and COD analysis. Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles demonstrated 84% removal of BB and 91% removal of BG dyes. The reusing catalytic capability of the Ce (0.05 M) doped PbMoO₄ product was also assessed with a slight diminish in the removal efficiency even after the five successive runs.

keywords— Photoluminescence (PL), Photocatalysis, Ce-PbMoO₄, COD, Reusability

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, challenges posed by climate change, industrial development, urban expansion and water pollution have become a significant environmental concern. The main factor contributing to this difficulty is the existence of environmental contaminants such as chemical pesticides, heavy metals, aromatic substances, medicines and synthetic dyes [1]. When the discharged waste from industrial effluents, is released into the surroundings without any proper treatment, is highly toxic to aquatic organisms and the environment. Degradation techniques have been employed recently to breakdown these dangerous contaminations using a variety of semiconductor materials [2], [3]. The degradation of pollutants through photocatalysis has emerged as an efficient technology for purifying air and water, with organic dyes widely used in textiles, leather, cosmetics, food, plastics and paper [4]. Nanomaterials have emerged as highly effective heterogeneous photocatalysts. Photocatalysts such as TiO₂ are highly regarded for their long term stability and non-toxic nature, leading to extensive application. However, their ability to absorb solar light is limited to a small fraction (5%) [5]. In comparison, molybdate a transition metal salt with similar properties to TiO₂, has attracted significant attention as a photocatalyst because of its effective light response and high surface area [6].

There are several molybdate materials applied for photocatalytic degradation process including PbMoO₄ [7], SrMoO₄ [8], NiMoO₄ [9], CdMoO₄ [10], CuMoO₄ [11], ZnMoO₄ [12], Zr(MoO₄)₂ [13], CoMoO₄ [14], Titanium molybdate [15], Cerium molybdate [16]. Molybdate materials are extensively researched due to their significant optical, electronic and magnetic properties [17]. Lead molybdate (PbMoO₄) is a compound that combines lead (Pb) with molybdate (MoO₄), which changes its properties and reduces its toxicity [18]. Various methods have been adopted for the synthesis of PbMoO₄ nanoparticles, including solid state reaction [19], crystal growth [20], microwave-assisted synthesis [21], sonochemical method [22], solvothermal route [23], precipitation method [2] and hydrothermal method [24]. The co-precipitation method is widely recognized for its simplicity, low cost and ease of synthesis. This method has garnered significant interest because it enables the formation of oxides characterized by

high crystallinity and dispersibility in aqueous media. It offers advantages such as reduced reaction times, lower synthesis temperature, precise control over reaction parameters, manipulation of product size and morphology, incorporation of dopants to enhance specific crystalline planes, improved product purity and material properties [25].

The photocatalytic activity of PbMoO_4 , known for its relatively wide bandgap, has predominantly been demonstrated under UV irradiation across various morphologies. Exploiting trap states within the PbMoO_4 bandgap hold promising extend photocatalytic efficacy in the visible light spectrum, although this approach remains unexplored. Current research indicates that the generation of charge carriers in PbMoO_4 crystals is primarily influenced by lattice defects, potentially arising from vacancies in Pb or O sites [26]. Doping and composite strategies offer viable avenues to narrow the bandgap of these metal molybdate. Specifically, doping PbMoO_4 with elements such as Ag [27], Gd [28], Co [29], Eu [30] and Yb [31] has been shown to significantly enhance its photodegradation capability. This enhancement is attributed to shifting the introduction of defects or new energy levels, the creation of oxygen vacancies in visible light absorption, and the prevention of recombination of photoexcited charge carriers [32].

Among these, cerium (Ce) rare-earth metal oxide is recognized for its cost-effectiveness, low toxicity, thermal stability and robust crystal attributes [16]. Ce ions, with oxidation states including Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} , contribute to versatile redox potential and effective oxygen storage capacity [33]. The majority of studies have been carried out using Ce doped titanium [34], Ce doped MoO_3 [35], Ce doped CaMoO_4 [36], Ce doped PbWO_4 [37], Ce^{3+} doped $\text{CeO}_2/\text{Bi}_2\text{MoO}_6$ [38], Ce doped ZrO_2 [39], Ce doped $\text{Mn}_3\text{Gd}_{7-x}\text{Ce}_x(\text{SiO}_4)_6\text{O}_1$ [40], Ce^{4+} doped Fe_3O_4 [41], and Ce doped ZnTiO_3 [42].

In this present study, PbMoO_4 and Ce (0.025, 0.050 and 0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles were synthesized by using the co-precipitation method. The products were analyzed by XRD, UV-DRS, SEM with EDS, HRTEM and PL. The photocatalytic activity was assessed against Brilliant Blue (BB) and Brilliant Green (BG). The Ce doped PbMoO_4 photocatalyst exhibited significantly improved photocatalytic activity compared to the pure PbMoO_4 . The possible degradation mechanism and the separation of charge carriers between PbMoO_4 and Ce ions are discussed.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

A. Materials

Cerous nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Lead nitrate ($\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$), Sodium molybdate ($\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Brilliant green ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$) and Brilliant blue ($\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{Na}_2\text{O}_9\text{S}_3$) were purchased from Merck and SD chemicals. All the chemical reagents (AR grade) were used without any further processing. Ethanol and ultrapure water were utilized for the dilution and sample preparation processes.

B. Synthesis of PbMoO_4 and Ce (0.025-0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles

Synthesis of PbMoO_4 and Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles were synthesized by co-precipitation technique. Specifically, 4.96 g (0.3 M) of Lead nitrate was dissolved in 50 ml of ultrapure water and stirred continuously for 15 min to ensure a uniform suspension. Subsequently, $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with different amounts of (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) powder was dissolved in 50 ml of ultrapure water and added to the above mixture, the aqueous solution was stirred for another 30 minutes. Then, 6.04 g of Sodium molybdate was dissolved in 50 ml of ultrapure water. With vigorous stirring, the solution was slowly added to the previous mixture. The combined mixture was then stirred for 5 h at 80°C . The resulting precipitate was filtered and rinsed multiple times with ultrapure water and ethanol. The collected precipitate was, dried at 100°C for 5 h and then calcined at 700°C for 4 hours. A similar procedure was followed to synthesize the PbMoO_4 nanoparticles.

C. Characterizations

The crystalline structure and phase determination of the products were analyzed by X-ray diffraction with Cu K α incident radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) using a Shimadzu XRD-6000. The photoluminescence (PL) of the sample was recorded in a fluorescence spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer, model: LS 45) with a range of 200 nm to 900 nm. Diffuse reflectance spectra were taken (UV-DRS) with the UV-2600 series reflectance mode. The microstructures and surface morphologies of the prepared sample were characterized by SEM combined with EDS (JEOL-JSM-IT 200). The shape, micrographs, and average size of samples were determined by using HRTEM (Jeol Japan, JEM-2100 Plus) analysis.

D. Photocatalytic measurements

The photocatalytic efficiency of the Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO $_4$ catalyst was evaluated under visible light irradiation using the degradation of BG and BB dyes. Approximately 8 mg of the synthesized catalyst was added to 250 ml glass beaker containing 150 ml of BB and BG solutions (Initial concentration: 3×10^{-5} M). The aqueous solutions were stirred effectively for 30 min under dark environment to allow the absorption and desorption of BB and BG dye solutions on the catalyst surface. The glass beakers were then placed in a photoreactor and irradiated with a 500 W visible lamp. At 15 min interval, 5 ml of the suspension was sampled and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min to remove particles from the suspension. Finally, changes in the absorption peaks of the supernatant suspensions were examined using UV-Vis measurements. The photocatalytic efficiency of the two dye substances was calculated using the following equation,

$$D = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where D denotes the percentage of degradation, C_0 is the initial and C_t is the dye concentration at a certain irradiation time (t) of both BB and BG dyes.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. XRD analysis

The XRD analysis investigated the crystal phase and crystallite size of the materials. Fig. 1 shows the diffraction peaks of PbMoO $_4$ and Ce doped PbMoO $_4$ samples. The XRD peaks indicate the tetragonal phase of the PbMoO $_4$ sample exhibits prominent peaks at 18 $^\circ$, 27 $^\circ$, 29 $^\circ$, 33 $^\circ$, 37 $^\circ$, 40 $^\circ$, 44 $^\circ$, 47 $^\circ$, 51 $^\circ$, 55 $^\circ$, 56 $^\circ$, 71 $^\circ$, 72 $^\circ$ and 78 $^\circ$, corresponding to the (101), (112), (004), (200), (114), (123), (204), (220), (116), (312), (224), (208), (316), and (404) planes as per JCPDS No. 44-1486 [30]. The XRD patterns of Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO $_4$ samples were similar to those of the PbMoO $_4$ sample. The sharp intensity peaks were observed, then the decrease in the intensity peaks with increasing Ce doping concentration. The sharp intensity peaks indicate that the products have excellent crystallinity [43], [44]. The crystallite sizes of PbMoO $_4$ and Ce doped PbMoO $_4$ product were calculated using the Scherrer equation,

$$D = \frac{\kappa\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad (2)$$

Here, D denotes the crystallite size, k indicates the constant number (0.9), λ indicates the wavelength of Cu-K α radiation (1.54056 Å), β indicates the full width at half maximum and θ denotes the diffraction angle. The crystallite sizes of the PbMoO $_4$ and Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO $_4$ samples were presented in Table I. Moreover, it was noted that the crystallite sizes were slightly increased and decreased with increasing Ce ion concentrations.

TABLE I
THE CRYSTALLITE SIZE, PHASES AND ENERGY GAP OF PURE AND Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) DOPED PbMoO₄

S. No.	Materials	Crystallite size (nm)	Phases	Energy gap (eV)
1.	PbMoO ₄	19.12	Tetragonal	3.12
2.	PbMoO ₄ : Ce (0.025 M)	20.65	Tetragonal	2.76, 2.28
3.	PbMoO ₄ : Ce (0.050 M)	22.23	Tetragonal	2.73, 2.24
4.	PbMoO ₄ : Ce (0.075 M)	19.80	Tetragonal	2.94, 2.33

Fig. 1 XRD pattern of PbMoO₄ and Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles

B. UV-Vis DRS analysis

The energy gaps and optical properties of the synthesized PbMoO₄ and Ce doped PbMoO₄ were observed through UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. Figures 2a and 2b show the absorption spectrum and energy gap of PbMoO₄ and Ce doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles. It is assumed that the PbMoO₄ and Ce doped PbMoO₄ exhibit the UV-absorption peak at 305 nm. Increasing the Ce concentration, the absorption peak slightly shifts toward a longer wavelength region compared with PbMoO₄ nanoparticles. The band gap energy of the nanoparticles decreases with the increase of Ce dopants as shown in Figure 2b. Lead molybdate recombination decreased the catalysts band gap ratio and raised its efficiency to absorb visible light [6]. The amount of Ce concentration and an additional impurity may create a new energy level between CB and VB of PbMoO₄. The band gap energy of PbMoO₄ and Ce doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles can be calculated according to the equation [45],

$$\alpha = \frac{A(h\nu - E_g)^{1/2}}{h\nu} \quad (3)$$

Where α , E_g , A and $h\nu$ are the absorption coefficient, energy gap, the proportionality constant and photon energy respectively. The energy gap of pure and Ce doped PbMoO_4 samples were measured by plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus the photon energy ($h\nu$). The energy gap for PbMoO_4 and Ce doped PbMoO_4 were listed in Table I.

Fig. 2 Absorption spectra (a) and Band gap energy (b) of pure PbMoO_4 and Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles

C. SEM with EDS analysis

The morphological features of the optimized Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 were characterized by SEM analysis. The Ce (0.05 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles at dissimilar magnification exhibited spherical structures with little agglomeration as shown in Fig. 3a and 3b. The elemental composition of the optimized sample was further investigated by using EDS analysis. The obtained sample consists of Ce, Mo, Pb and O signals, denoting the successful preparation of Ce doped PbMoO_4 as shown in Fig. 3c. This indicates the purity of sample and no other impurities present in the prepared sample.

Fig. 3 (a, b) SEM images and (c) EDS analysis of Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles

D. HRTEM analysis

The microstructure, shape and size of Ce (0.05 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles were investigated by HRTEM images with different magnification, SAED patterns and lattice fringes, as shown in Fig. 4(a-e). From this micrograph (Fig. 4(a, b)), it is seen that the nanoparticles are spherical in shape with slight agglomeration. The edge spacing is 0.320 nm and 0.204 nm, which corresponds to the interfacial spacing of the (112) and (204) planes of the tetragonal PbMoO₄ phase (Fig. 4d). The SAED image of optimized nanoparticles exhibits clear ring structures and polycrystalline nature as denoted in Fig. 4c. These results are in good agreement with those of the XRD analysis. The average size of the Ce (0.05 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles is 22.52 nm calculated using the histogram, depicted in figure 4e.

Fig. 4 HRTEM images of Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles (a, b), SEAD pattern (c), lattice fringes (d) and Histogram (e)

E. PL spectroscopy

The PL spectra of pure and Ce (0.025, 0.050 and 0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles were recorded at an excitation wavelength of 305 nm. In figure 5, the pure nanoparticles exhibit three weak emission peaks at 340, 455, 479 and one strong emission peak at 608 nm. Whereas, Ce (0.025, 0.050 and 0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles exhibit three emission peaks at 385, 479, 525 nm and one sharp peak at 608 nm. The inhomogeneous crystalline size distribution, in plane crystallite orientation and surface defects may all contribute to enhanced PL properties [32], [39]. The sample exhibits broad green-blue emission peaks at 455, 479 and 525 nm, attributed to extrinsic transitions caused by structural defects [11] and at 385 nm due to electron recombination in the blue region. The electron transfer properties of PbMoO_4 nanoparticles are evident due to their excellent crystallinity [46]. Hence, the green-blue PL emission is attributed to intrinsic slight distortions in the $[\text{MoO}_4]$ tetrahedron, consistent with findings in previous literature. Additionally, red emissions may arise from disorders at long-range and medium-range scales. This type of disordered powder shows promise for various applications in photosynthesis, photocatalysis and photovoltaic conversion, owing to its broad light response range from violet to red-visible light [47].

Fig. 5 PL emission spectra of pure PbMoO_4 and Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles

F. Photocatalytic investigations

The photocatalytic activities of the Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalyst were evaluated by degrading BG and BB dye solutions under visible irradiation. The strong, broad and slightly weaker absorption peaks of BG and BB dye solutions with the Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalyst are shown in Figures 6 and 7. In addition, a blank experiment under irradiation without a photocatalyst was detected. The photocatalytic performance of Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 nanoparticles is analyzed by plotting (C/C_0) as a function of time for BG and BB dyes as shown in figure 8. The Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalyst exhibits better photodegradation properties, of about 91% and 84% in (BG and BB) dye solutions respectively, it could be photodegraded within 120 min. The result indicates that the photodegradation efficiencies of pure PbMoO_4 and Ce doped PbMoO_4 catalyst surfaces with visible irradiation were achieved within 120 min. With

almost 41%, 80%, 78% for BB and 49%, 86%, 82% for BG dyes degradation had been ascertained for pure PbMoO_4 , Ce (0.025 M) PbMoO_4 , Ce (0.075 M) PbMoO_4 catalyst respectively (not presented).

Among them Ce (0.05 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalysts exhibits photodegradation efficiency of 91% degradation for BG and 84% degradation for BB dye solutions. These results revealed an improved photocatalytic activity of Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalyst compared to PbMoO_4 under visible light irradiation. Table II displayed the rate of Chemical-Oxygen-Demand (COD) values and the mineralization of both (BB and BG) dye substances. However, the removal was regarded by the COD analysis. After 120 min of illumination with Ce (0.05 M) doped PbMoO_4 , 78% (BB) and 83% (BG) of COD reduction are received. One of the reasons for the doped PbMoO_4 catalysts high activity could be the attachment of Ce to the surface of the host material. This prevents photoinduced e^- and h^+ recombination, resulting in better charge separation than PbMoO_4 . This may be responsible for the improved photocatalytic activity of the Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 photocatalyst.

Fig. 6 Absorption spectra of Brilliant Green (BG) dye solution displaying photocatalytic degradation using Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalysts.

Fig. 7 Absorption spectra of Brilliant Blue (BB) dye solution displaying photocatalytic degradation using Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalysts.

Fig. 8 Degradation of BB and BG dyes with Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMo₄ nanoparticles for different irradiation time intervals.

TABLE II

PERCENTAGE COD REDUCTION OF BB AND BG SUBSTANCES USING Ce (0.050 M) DOPED PbMo₄ CATALYST

S. No.	Irradiation time (min)	% COD removal for BB dye: Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMo ₄	% COD removal for BG dye: Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMo ₄
1	15	26	31
2	30	37	40
3	45	64	54
4	60	65	61
5	75	66	71
6	90	68	73
7	105	73	81
8	120	78	83

G. Reusability test

To assess the reusability of Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMo₄ catalysts were collected at each end of the catalytic reaction. In each experiment, samples were retrieved from the treated solution through centrifugation, followed by multiple washes using distilled water and ethanol. Subsequently, the samples were dried at 100°C for 90 minutes, then a new dye solution was applied for further testing. From Table III, it can be confirmed that after five reuse cycles the dye degradation capacity was decreased to BB-79% and BG-84% for Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMo₄ samples, respectively.

TABLE III

REUSABILITY OF Ce (0.050 M) DOPED PbMo₄ CATALYST FOR THE CONTINUOUS DEGRADATION OF BB AND BG DYES.

S. No.	Number of cycles	Degradation (%) efficiency	
		BB dye	BG dye
1	1	84	91
2	2	83	90
3	3	83	88
4	4	81	87
5	5	79	84

H. Scavenger study

To explore the impact of reactive species generated during the co-precipitation of Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 in an aqueous solution, the influence of various surfactants on the degradation of BG and BB was examined. The degradation efficiency of BG (91%, 78%, 65%, 60% and 55%), BB (84%, 63%, 62%, 58% and 47%) in the presence of without scavenger, n-butyl alcohol (n-BuOH), tetra butyl ammonium hydroxide (TBAH), sodium fluoride (NaF) and L-ascorbic acid (L-AA) respectively. The degradation efficiency of both BG and BB dye were significantly reduced after the addition of L-AA, NaF, which acts as an $\cdot\text{OH}^-$, h^+ scavenger. n-BuOH and TBAH purification acting as superoxide radicals, the degradation efficiency decreased slightly. On the other hand, complete decay of BG and BB was obtained by periodic addition, which was acting as an e^- scavenger. The results suggest that h^+ and $\cdot\text{OH}^-$ radicals act as minor and major scavenger species for both dyes (BB and BG) removals (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9 Different scavenger study on degradation of both BB and BG dye substances in Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalysts under visible irradiation

I. Degradation mechanism

The photocatalytic mechanism of BB and BG dye degradation over Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 catalyst under visible light irradiation is illustrated in Figure 10. The band gap of both dye solutions over Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO_4 sample lies in the visible range. Hence the visible light was applied for testing of prepared catalyst for the degradation of both dye solutions. The Ce- PbMoO_4 catalyst generated electron (e^-) and hole (h^+) pairs. The generated e^- simultaneously may transfer to the conduction band (CB) to Ce energy levels and generated h^+ in the valence band (VB). The photogenerated e^- in the CB allowed a reaction with surrounding O_2 molecules to produce superoxide radicals ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$). In addition, the generated h^+ further reacts with hydroxyl molecules and produce the hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}^-$). These extremely reactive superoxide radicals and hydroxyl radicals are most responsible for enhancing in the photocatalytic activity. Primary active species, consisting of free $\text{e}^- - \text{h}^+$, catalyze oxidation/reduction reactions to transform molecular oxygen and water into secondary active free radicals, namely $\cdot\text{O}_2^-/\cdot\text{OH}^-$. These extremely reactive free radicals react with organic BG and BB dyes, causing them to decompose into simpler, harmless substances (H_2O , CO_2) [48]. The potential reactions reporting the above discussed matter are given in the following equations 4-8,

Fig. 10 Schematic representation of photocatalytic degradation mechanism of BB and BG dyes in Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO₄

IV. CONCLUSION

The pure PbMoO₄ and Ce (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 M) doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles were successfully prepared by the co-precipitation method. The XRD peak shows a tetragonal phase of pure and the peak intensity decreased with an increase in Cerium concentration. The modified energy gap and reduction in PL emission peak prevent the separation efficiency of photoexcited charge carriers remarkably improves degradation efficiency. DRS observation indicates a decrease in the bandgap energy due to an increase in Cerium concentration. SEM and HRTEM results showed that the particles are spherical in shape and some particles are slightly agglomerated. The photocatalytic efficiency of Brilliant Green (BG-91%) and Brilliant Blue (BB-84%) dye solutions under visible light irradiation. The Ce (0.050 M) doped PbMoO₄ product observed to be reusable and COD measures affirm the complete destruction of both BG and BB dye molecules.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank Dr. P. Senthilkumar, Professor of Chemical Engineering and Head, Centre of Excellence in Water Research (CEWAR), Sri Sivasubramaniya Nadar College of Engineering, Kalavakkam, 603 110, Tamil Nadu, India, for recording of all application part, like Photocatalyst, Scavenger studies, COD studies, Catalyst dosage, Reusability measurements.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. A. Adegoke, and O. S. Bello, "Dye sequestration using agricultural wastes as adsorbents," *Water resources and industry*, 12, 8-24, 2015.
- [2] M. Rajkumar, M. Arunpandian, K. Leeladevi, P. Rameshkumar, and S. Arunachalam, "Fabrication of pebble stone-like PbMoO₄ nanostructure: Focus on photocatalysis, photoluminescence and electron density distribution analysis," *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, 620, 413222, 2021.
- [3] S. K. Ray, and J. Hur, "Surface modifications, perspectives, and challenges of scheelite metal molybdate photocatalysts for removal of organic pollutants in wastewater," *Ceramics International*, 46(13), 20608-20622, 2020.
- [4] S. Asha, C. Hentry, M. R. Bindhu, A. M. Al-Mohameed, M. R. AbdelGawwad, M. S. Elshikh, "Improved photocatalytic activity for degradation of textile dyeing waste water and thiazine dyes using PbWO₄ nanoparticles synthesized by co-precipitation method," *Environmental Research*, 200, 111721, 2021.
- [5] F. Duan, Y. Zheng, and M. Chen, "Enhanced photocatalytic activity of bismuth molybdate via hybridization with carbon," *Materials letters*, 65(2), 191-193, 2011.
- [6] H. Chang, H. Yi, Q. Ke, and J. Zhang, "Preparation of a AgCl/PbMoO₄ composite and investigation of its photocatalytic oxidative desulfurization performance," *ACS omega*, 5(19), 10927-10938, 2020.
- [7] D. Errandonea, D. Santamaria-Perez, V. Grover, S. N. Achary, A. K. Tyagi, "High-pressure x-ray diffraction study of bulk and nanocrystalline PbMoO₄," *Journal of Applied Physics*, 108(7), 2010.
- [8] T. Thongtem, S. Kungwankunakorn, B. Kuntalue, A. Phuruangrat, and S. Thongtem, "Luminescence and absorbance of highly crystalline CaMoO₄, SrMoO₄, CaWO₄ and SrWO₄ nanoparticles synthesized by co-precipitation method at room temperature," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 506(1), 475-481, 2010.
- [9] S. K. Ray, D. Dhakal, Y. K. Kshetri, and S. W. Lee, "Cu- α -NiMoO₄ photocatalyst for degradation of Methylene blue with pathways and antibacterial performance," *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 348, 18-32, 2017.
- [10] W. S. Wang, L. Zhen, C. Y. Xu, W. Z. Shao, and Z. L. Chen, "Eu³⁺-doped CdMoO₄ red phosphor synthesized through an aqueous solution route at room temperature," *Journal of alloys and compounds*, 529, 17-20, 2012.
- [11] M. Benchikhi, R. El Ouattib, S. Guillemet-Fritsch, L. Er-Rakho, and B. Durand, "Characterization and photoluminescence properties of ultrafine copper molybdate (α -CuMoO₄) powders prepared via a combustion-like process," *International Journal of Minerals, Metallurgy, and Materials*, 23, 1340-1345, 2016.
- [12] I. Raya, A. A. Mansoor Al Sarraf, G. Widjaja, S. Ghazi Al-Shawi, M. F. Ramadan, Z. H. Mahmood, and H. Ghaleb Maabreh, "ZnMoO₄ nanoparticles: novel and facile synthesis, characterization, and photocatalytic performance," *Journal of Nanostructures*, 12(2), 446-454, 2022.
- [13] A. M. Amanulla, R. Sundaram, and K. Kaviyarasu, "An investigation of structural, magnetical, optical, antibacterial and humidity sensing of Zr (MoO₄) 2-ZrO₂ nanocomposites," *Surfaces and Interfaces*, 16, 132-140, 2019.
- [14] A. Habibi-Yangjeh, M. Mousavi, and K. Nakata, K. "Boosting visible-light photocatalytic performance of g-C₃N₄/Fe₃O₄ anchored with CoMoO₄ nanoparticles: novel magnetically recoverable photocatalysts," *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 368, 120-136, 2019.
- [15] A. Mobeen, C. M. Magdalane, S. J. Shahina, D. Lakshmi, R. Sundaram, G. Ramalingam, and K. Kaviyarasu, "Investigation on antibacterial and photocatalytic degradation of Rhodamine-B dye under visible light irradiation by titanium molybdate nanoparticles prepared via microwave method," *Surfaces and Interfaces*, 17, 100381, 2019.
- [16] A. Javaid, M. Imran, F. Kanwal, S. Latif, S. F. Adil, M. R. Shaik, M. Khan, "Sb-Doped Cerium Molybdate: An Emerging Material as Dielectric and Photocatalyst for the Removal of Diclofenac Potassium from Aqueous Media," *Molecules*, 28(24), 7979, 2023.
- [17] G. M. Gurgel, L. X. Lovisa, O. L. A. Conceição, M. S. Li, E. Longo, C. A. Paskocimas, and M. R. D. Bomio, "Evaluation of morphology and photoluminescent properties of PbMoO₄ crystals by ultrasonic amplitude," *Journal of Materials Science*, 52, 4608-4620, 2017.
- [18] Y. Wu, X. Cheng, X. Zhang, Y. Xu, S. Gao, H. Zhao, and L. Huo, "High efficient and selective removal of Pb²⁺ through formation of lead molybdate on α -MoO₃ porous nanosheets array," *Journal of colloid and interface science*, 491, 80-88, 2017.
- [19] S. C. Sabharwal, Sangeeta, and D. G. Desai, "Investigations of single crystal growth of PbMoO₄," *Crystal growth & design*, 6(1), 58-62, 2006.
- [20] D. Piwowarska, S. M. Kaczmarek, and M. Berkowski, "Dielectric, optical and EPR studies of PbMoO₄ single crystals, pure and doped with cobalt ions," *Journal of non-crystalline solids*, 354(35-39), 4437-4442, 2008.
- [21] D. B. Hernández-Uresti, A. Martínez-De La Cruz, and J. A. Aguilar-Garib, "Photocatalytic activity of PbMoO₄ molybdate synthesized by microwave method," *Catalysis today*, 212, 70-74, 2013.
- [22] A. Phuruangrat, T. Thongtem, and S. Thongtem, "Analysis of lead molybdate and lead tungstate synthesized by a sonochemical method," *Current Applied Physics*, 10(1), 342-345, 2010.
- [23] G. J. Xing, R. Liu, C. Zhao, Y. L. Li, Y. Wang, and G. M. Wu, "Photoluminescence and photocatalytic properties of uniform PbMoO₄ polyhedral crystals synthesized by microemulsion-based solvothermal method," *Ceramics International*, 37(7), 2951-2956, 2011.
- [24] A. Martínez-de la Cruz, D. B. Hernández-Uresti, L. M. Torres-Martínez, and S. W. Lee, "Photocatalytic properties of PbMoO₄ synthesized by a hydrothermal reaction," *Reaction Kinetics, Mechanisms and Catalysis*, 107(2), 467-475, 2012.
- [25] V. D. Araújo, R. L. Tranquilin, F. V. D. Motta, C. A. Paskocimas, M. I. B. Bernardi, L. S. Cavalcante, and M. R. D. Bomio, "Effect of polyvinyl alcohol on the shape, photoluminescence and photocatalytic properties of PbMoO₄ microcrystals," *Materials science in semiconductor processing*, 26, 425-430, 2014.
- [26] R. S. Datta, J. Z. Ou, M. D. Mohiuddin, B. J. Carey, B. Y. Zhang, B. H. Khan, and K. Kalantar-zadeh, "Two dimensional PbMoO₄: A photocatalytic material derived from a naturally non-layered crystal," *Nano Energy*, 49, 237-246, 2018.
- [27] G. Gyawali, R. Adhikari, B. Joshi, T. H. Kim, V. Rodríguez-González, and S. W. Lee, "Sonochemical synthesis of solar-light-driven Ag⁰-PbMoO₄ photocatalyst," *Journal of hazardous materials*, 263, 45-51, 2013.
- [28] A. Phuruangrat, S. Thongtem, and T. Thongtem, "Synthesis and characterization of Gd-doped PbMoO₄ nanoparticles used for UV-light-driven photocatalysis," *Journal of Rare Earths*, 39(9), 1056-1061, 2021.
- [29] D. Piwowarska, P. Gnutek, and C. Rudowicz, "Modeling the zero-field splitting parameters and local structure of Co²⁺ ions doped into PbMoO₄ crystal based on crystal field approach and superposition model analysis," *Optical Materials*, 84, 466-474, 2018.
- [30] J. Zhang, T. Zhao, L. Zou, and S. Gan, "Ultrasound-assisted precipitation synthesis of PbMoO₄ and PbMoO₄: Eu³⁺ nanocrystals and photoluminescence properties," *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 314, 35-41, 2016.
- [31] I. Trabelsi, M. Dammak, R. Maalej, and M. Kamoun, "Theoretical and comparative investigations of Yb³⁺ ion in MWO₄ and M' MoO₄ scheelites crystals (M= Sr, Pb, Ca, Ba) and (M'= Sr, Pb, Ca, Cd)," *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, 406(3), 315-318, 2011.
- [32] M. R. D. Bomio, L. S. Cavalcante, M. A. P. Almeida, R. L. Tranquilin, N. C. Batista, P. S. Pizani, and E. Longo, "Structural refinement, growth mechanism, infrared/Raman spectroscopies and photoluminescence properties of PbMoO₄ crystals," *Polyhedron*, 50(1), 532-545, 2013.
- [33] M. Sabarinathan, Y. Hayakawa, and S. Harish, "Cerium-doped MoS₂ layered nanostructures for enhanced photocatalytic activity under visible light illumination," *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 33(17), 13988-14000, 2022.
- [34] P. Ellappan, and L. R. Miranda, "Synthesis and characterization of cerium doped titanium catalyst for the degradation of nitrobenzene using visible light," *International Journal of Photoenergy*, 2014(1), 756408, 2014.
- [35] H. M. T. Farid, S. Aman, N. Ahmad, H. M. Abo-Dief, A. K. Alanazi, R. Y. Khosa, and Z. M. El-Bahy, "Ce-Doped MoO₃ Photocatalyst as an Environmental Purifier for Removal of Noxious Rhodamine B Organic Pollutant in Wastewater," *Energy Technology*, 11(7), 2300116, 2023.
- [36] A. Phuruangrat, S. Thongtem, and T. Thongtem, "Effect of Ce dopant on photocatalytic properties of CaMoO₄ nanoparticles prepared by microwave-assisted method," *Materials Research Innovations*, 26(2), 84-90, 2022.

- [37] D. Tawde, M. Srinivas, and K. V. R. Murthy, "Effect of lead source and cerium (III) doping on structural and photoluminescence properties of PbWO₄ microcrystallites synthesized by hydrothermal method," *physica status solidi (a)*, 208(4), 803-807, 2011.
- [38] G. Yang, Y. Liang, K. Li, J. Yang, R. Xu, and X. Xie, "Construction of a Ce³⁺ doped CeO₂/Bi₂ MoO₆ heterojunction with a mutual component activation system for highly enhancing the visible-light photocatalytic activity for removal of TC or Cr (VI)," *Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers*, 6(6), 1507-1517, 2019.
- [39] D. K. Verma, N. Shukla, B. Kumar, A. K. Singh, K. Shahu, M. Yadav, and R. B. Rastogi, "Synergistic tribo-activity of nanohybrids of zirconia/cerium-doped zirconia nanoparticles with nano lamellar reduced graphene oxide and molybdenum disulfide," *Nanomaterials*, 10(4), 707, 2020.
- [40] J. Fu, N. Liu, L. Mei, L. Liao, D. Deyneko, J. Wang, and G. Lv, "Synthesis of Ce-doped Mn₃Gd_{7-x}Cex (SiO₄)₆O_{1.5} for the enhanced catalytic ozonation of tetracycline," *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 18734, 2019.
- [41] N. A. Neto, L. E. D. Nascimento, M. Correa, F. Bohn, M. R. D. Bomio, and F. V. Motta, "Characterization and photocatalytic application of Ce⁴⁺, Co²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Ni²⁺ doped Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles obtained by the co-precipitation method," *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 242, 122489, 2020.
- [42] H. Eskandarloo, A. Badiie, M. A. Behnajady, A. Tavakoli, and G. M. Ziarani, "Ultrasonic-assisted synthesis of Ce doped cubic-hexagonal ZnTiO₃ with highly efficient sonocatalytic activity," *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, 29, 258-269, 2016.
- [43] G. Rajesh, P. S. Kumar, S. Akilandeswari, G. Rangasamy, S. Lohita, V. U. Shankar, K. Thirumalai, Strategies for ameliorating the photodegradation efficiency of Mn-doped CdAl₂O₄ nanoparticles for the toxic dyes under visible light illumination, *Chemosphere* 321, 138069, 2023.
- [44] M. Dargahi, M. Masteri-Farahani, S. Shahsavari, and M. Feizi, "Microemulsion-mediated preparation of Ce₂(MoO₄)₃ nanoparticles for photocatalytic degradation of crystal violet in aqueous solution," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27, 12047-12054, 2020.
- [45] G. Rajesh, P. S. Kumar, S. Akilandeswari, G. Rangasamy, A. Mandal, V. U. Shankar, K. Thirumalai, A synergistic consequence of catalyst dosage, pH solution and reactive species of Fe-doped CdAl₂O₄ nanoparticles on the degradation of toxic environmental pollutants, *Chemosphere* 318, 137919 (2023)
- [46] S. P. Keerthana, B. J. Rani, R. Yuvakkumar, G. Ravi, Y. Shivatharsiny, E. S. Babu, and D. Velauthapillai, "Copper molybdate nanoparticles for electrochemical water splitting application," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 46(11), 7701-7711, 2021.
- [47] A. B. Campos, A. Z. Simões, E. Longo, J. A. Varela, V. M. Longo, A. T. De Figueiredo, and A. C. Hernandez, "Mechanisms behind blue, green, and red photoluminescence emissions in CaWO₄ and CaMoO₄ powders. Applied physics letters, 91(5), 051923, 2007.
- [48] G. Rajesh, P. S. Kumar, G. Rangasamy, S. Akilandeswari, A. Mandal, V. U. Shankar, K. Thirumalai, Fabrication of a novel Ni-doped CdAl₂O₄ nanoparticles and applications in photo-oxidation processes under visible light illumination, *Molecular Catalysis*, 535, 112835, 2023.